
FINANCIAL LITERACY EMPOWERS WOMEN

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ABSTRACT

In this Digital world, financial literacy is mandatory to overcome any pitfalls. After Covid Pandemic situation, Indian economy has changed dramatically and due to increased market complexity and exposure to advanced technology, individuals' financial responsibility has increased. Earnings in Lakhs and lavish spending, impulse buying, increased digital scams has been a burden to the Indian Government. To overcome these difficulties and to enhance economic development, Government, RBI, SEBI and other financial institution's key focus is to financially literate the people of India. Role of Women in contributing towards the economy has increased hence the digital literacy and financial literacy of women is noteworthy. Only limited number of females are aware of financial management. Financial literacy means the capacity to understand and use various financial skills. Budgeting, savings and investments are referred to as financial literacy. It helps people in making solid financial choices by ensuring long-term financial security and well-being.

Financial Literacy is a key indicator of a growing economy. Secondary data and research studies reveal that the women's financial literacy is very poor. Secondary data was collected from websites, journals, newspapers, and various regulatory bodies. This paper probes into the Government initiatives, RBI and SEBI efforts and other financial institution efforts to impart financial education through campaigns, workshops seminars so as to guide people to manage money more effectively, overcome any pitfalls and to achieve financial well-being.

Keywords financial literacy, financial inclusion, empowerment

Introduction

Today's youth learn more than ever before and are becoming financial consumers earlier in their lives. It is essential for them to make financial decisions that can have lasting consequences, if not well managed it will lead

to failures. Women are competing with men in all spheres. The modern woman has begun to unlock her true potential and is dominating in business, politics, sports, entertainment, literature, space science and technology. Globally, financial literacy becomes essential to enable each and every one to save the hard earned money so as to navigate any challenges and hardships. Lack of Financial literacy leads life in dramatic ways. Health is wealth, but in the current scenario, financial wealth is essential to maintain good health.

After Covid Pandemic situation, mobile plays a dominant role in the lives of all class of people. Today earning money is a simple task but managing this earned money and building money makes money concept is possible only because of financial knowledge. Moreover, in the year of 2025, many digital tools proliferate and financial products grow more complex, understanding basic financial concepts are no longer optional, it is mandatory.

Financial literacy

Financial literacy means the capacity to understand and use various financial skills. Budgeting and saving is referred to as financial literacy. It helps people in making solid financial choices by ensuring long-term financial security and well-being. The following are the key financial skills:

Budgeting means understanding how to create and manage income and expenses and it is essential for financial stability.

Investing refers to the knowledge of investment options and strategies that help to build wealth and achieve long-term financial goals. Every one save to meet huge expenses such as higher education, house, marriage and car and so on.

Retirement Planning: Planning for retirement is critical to ensure financial security in the long term.

Debt Management: Understanding how to manage debt and build a good credit score is vital for financial health.

Financial Literacy among Women

Women make up a sizable share of Indian homemakers, so it's a must for them to have essential financial knowledge. Modern women contribute a lot for the economic development of the nation but their standard of living needs to be enhanced by injecting financial knowledge in their minds. This knowledge is essential for them to run the household and provide for all of the dependents' financial needs.

Financial inclusion means irrespective of one's financial status, geographical location, or social status one has access to essential financial services like savings accounts, insurance, credit, and other payment systems. In recent times, financial inclusion is a key driver of economic growth and alleviation of poverty across the globe. An individual needs to be financially literate to make full use of financial services. Financial inclusion of women in India is lagging. It is imperative to equip women with financial literacy so that they can accumulate financial reserves. This is an important safeguard against unforeseen and unfortunate circumstances.

An African proverb says, "If you educate a man you educate an individual. But if you educate a woman, you educate a nation". Financial literacy among working women is crucial for achieving economic independence, confidence, and security. It enables them to make informed decisions about their finances, investments, and retirement planning. Financial inclusions empower women as effective management of finance paves path for reducing dependence on others. Women explore entrepreneurial ventures and contribute for economic development and a financially literate woman builds a sustainable future.

Review of Literature

According to the Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) Report 2023, only 35% of men and 30% of women are financially literate across the globe. In India, a study by the Securities and Exchange Board of India (SEBI) reveals that only 27% of men and 20% of women are financially literate.

Chetna Singh & Raj Kumar (2017) in their study revealed that it is very crucial to financially literate the women to fuel the engine of growth by providing opportunities to women to contribute to economic growth. While women in developed countries proved to be better financial planners relatively, it is the women of emerging

economies who have to become literate when it comes to money management issues. Though various initiatives were taken by different organisations to boost the financial literacy but still there is a need of more awareness programs which may include workshops, seminars, and financial management courses at different levels to get more financial knowledge regarding the banking services and their benefits one can attend.

Somiha Chatterjee (2021) expressed in her study that the goal of making financial services available through digital platforms is to reduce poverty and contribute to a generally more inclusive financial playing field. However, women's limited access to these digital technologies in India poses the danger of pushing them towards the wrong side of a persistent digital divide.

According to the Humanity Welfare Council, around 62% of Indian women do not own bank accounts or have limited access to banking services. Considering gender pay gaps, the lower income makes them vulnerable to economic shocks such as long debts and lower opportunities. More than half the population lack social coverage due to lack of public investment in a social safety net.

Digitalisation is one of the most influential mega global trends of today and government worldwide are making strides at increasing financial inclusion by boosting access to digital bank accounts and other digital financial services. The adoption of digital payments across the world was boosted by COVID-19 and digital payments, in turn, have widened financial inclusion. However, without this financial literacy these opportunities might lead to defaults, debts and financial hardships.

Challenges Faced by Women

- Women are paid lower than men, affecting their ability to save and invest for the future.
- Practically many women lack confidence in managing finances as they lack financial education.
- Decision making by women is denied in most of the families and community.
- Women mobility in India is highly limited.

- Indian women have to balance both family and business. They give emphasis to family ties and relationship. The burden of these overlapping duties can limit their time and energy to focus on financial management.
- Women priorities savings but they are not ready to venture in to risky investments.
- Societal Norms restricts women to prove their personalities in an innovative , daring, competitive jobs.
- Women prefer to invest in physical gold. They are ready to learn the money making oppurtunities in stock market.
- Most of the women are not aware of the mutual fund.
- Women prefer quick money so they fall prey to unregistered chit funds.
- In most families there is no financial transparency and financial decisions are denied for women.
- A lower credit score can limit their ability to secure loans or obtain favourable interest rates.

Financial Literacy - Women's Prosperity

As women increasingly take on diverse roles in society and the workforce, financial education has become more crucial than ever. Mastering financial literacy enables a woman to achieve financial independence and stability. It opens doors to opportunities and ensures a secure financial future. By enhancing financial education, women can confidently navigate their financial journeys and make informed decisions that benefit themselves and their families. Financial literacy becomes essential for securing a stable and comfortable future.

Various government schemes focus on supporting women to overcome societal challenges. Self-help groups, and development programmes, such as FLCC (Financial Literacy and Credit Counselling Centres), National Center for Financial Education (NCFE), etc., continue to develop and disseminate financial literacy resources through relevant projects and campaigns. In addition, initiatives such as Pradhan Mantri Jan-Dhan, and 'BetiBachao, BetiPadhao' have added to the effectiveness of welfare programmes focused on women

empowerment. Apart from this the government has introduced many schemes that can help women today.

Schemes such as Orient MahilaVikasYojna, Stree Shakti, Udyogini, and more exist to uplift women financially.

National Centre for Financial Education (NCFE) is a Company (Not for Profit), registered under section 8 of the Companies Act 2013, promoted by Reserve bank of India (RBI), Securities and Exchange Board of India (SEBI), Insurance Regulatory and Development Authority of India (IRDAI), and Pension Fund Regulatory and Development Authority (PFRDA) to promote Financial Education across India for all sections of the population. Its vision is to undertake initiatives to make the country financially aware and empowered. In view of the said vision, NCFE carries out a significant amount of financial education campaign to help people manage money more effectively to achieve financial well - being by accessing appropriate financial products and services through regulated entities with fair and transparent machinery for consumer protection and grievance redressal.

National Centre for Financial Education has introduced FACT (Financial Awareness and Consumer Training), a program specifically designed to provide financial education to young graduates and postgraduates. This program covers topics relevant to this demographic, aiming to positively impact their financial well-being. By equipping the youth with the knowledge and skills necessary for informed financial decision-making, FACT contributes to building a financially savvy and responsible generation.

Financial Literacy Week 2025 was observed during February 24 – 28, 2025 and the theme is 'Financial Literacy - Women's Prosperity' with emphasis on 'Financial Planning', 'Saving and Risk Management' and 'Availing Credit for Growth'.

Financial Inclusion and Education are two important elements in the Reserve Bank of India's developmental role. Towards this, it has created critical volume of literature and has uploaded on its website in 13 languages for banks and other stakeholders to download and use. The aim of this initiative is to create awareness about financial products and services, good financial practices, going digital and consumer protection. Business Correspondents (BCs) are retail agents that provide doorstep banking services in rural areas.

Smile Foundation's Swabhiman program strives to bridge the gender gap in financial literacy, promote economic empowerment, and contribute to the overall well-being of rural women and their communities.

"Education is more valuable than Money, in the long run", emphasis Robert Kiyosaki Author of Rich Dad Poor Dad. Education empowers women wherein they must learn effective budgeting as it is essential for gaining control over expenses, maximizing savings and working towards achieving important financial goals. Women must be educated to understand loan terms, interest rates and repayment schedules. Knowledge of debt management must be imparted. Women must be well informed of the power of compounding. Employers can arrange meetings to educate their Women employees about the Provident fund, pension schemes, Life and health insurance schemes that focus on their wellbeing. Women must be trained to analyze and understand various investment options such as gold, stocks, bonds, real estate, and mutual funds as it is crucial for building a diverse and resilient investment portfolio. Don't follow the crowd for quick money. Financial advisor's advice to opt for systematic investment plan (SIP) and the amount is calculated based on one's age and the period money is required. Financial advisors and Government agencies can conduct seminars to educate women to have a diversified portfolio based on her financial goals. Financial institutions must troubleshoot issues faced by women in digital adoption. Demonstrating and understanding of how inflation affects purchasing power must be made clear and the effect of impulse buying and online shopping must be well defined and the steps to avoid them must be clearly explained through workshops and seminars. Women are more likely to take career breaks. These breaks can result in income loss and reduced retirement savings. They must be trained to predict and tackle this situation through their strong diversified portfolio.

Financial literacy can educate women in building a good credit score. A good credit score not only reflects responsible financial behaviour but also opens doors to improved financial opportunities. Financial literacy campaign can focus on making aware of women about Tax benefit- ELSS - tax saving mutual funds. In this digital era, training can be given on E – LMS & Financial Literacy Mobile App of NCFE. To improve their economic

wellbeing Women must come forward to attend webinars, signing up for online courses, reading financial books, and following trusted financial websites. Above all family must include women in financial planning and there must be transparency moreover the family members must be well informed about the loans, borrowings and investments.

Conclusion

Women frequently juggle in multiple roles wherein effective planning paves path for them to overcome the obstacles. Financial planning promotes wellbeing. Financial inclusion and financial literacy are no longer personal advantage, it's a societal necessity. Financial literacy and digital literacy are mandatory for women. Further women must master in Budgeting, investment planning and risk diversification which are the key ingredients of financial literacy. Inflation knowledge, SIP and interest compounding must be imparted to empower women. Tech savvy women must be an expert in handling finance and train others also grew as a financially savvy and responsible generation. Digital Financial Literacy Programs must propel women to play a meaningful role in India's economic success.

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